

Most Cited Articles in Academia

**International Journal of Computer Science and
Engineering Survey (IJCSES)**

ISSN: 0976-2760 (Online); 0976-3252 (Print)

<http://airccse.org/journal/ijcses/index.html>

Review and Analysis on Telecommunication Networks Infrastructure in the Northwest Province of Nigeria for Optimisation: Problems and Solutions

Sanusi Mohammed Bunu¹, Murtala Muhammad² and Hamid Abubakar Adamu³,

¹ Adamawa State Polytechnic, Nigeria, ² Adamawa State University Mubi, Nigeria and ³ Adamawa State University Mubi, Nigeria

ABSTRACT

Telecommunication network infrastructure determines the strength of a country for successful communication with other parts of the world. Due to the rapid increase of internet usage and mobile communication in every part of the world, specifically the third world countries, Nigeria is among the countries that is advancing in the used of telecommunication contraptions. The Nigerian Telecommunication Industries play a vital role in boosting the social and economic infrastructure of the country. This paper is aimed at investigating the Telecommunication Network infrastructure in the Northwestern part of Nigerian and propose some technologies that increase data bandwidth and internet penetration in the region. Problems and future solutions to the existing network infrastructure in the province were discussed and basic analysis is conducted to justify the importance of the study. Mobile market analysis, current infrastructure, parameters evaluation and the way forward to the problems are discussed. Comparative analysis between the existing network infrastructure that is 3G networks and the proffer solution to the existing standard which is 4G network is also conducted. This paper also conducts an analysis on the existing Network providers in the region with their draw backs and the quality of services they provide to the customers within the region. The paper concludes with a future plan of coming up with an analytical solution in order to study the implementation process of a full 4G network in the Northwest region of Nigeria and to use a simulated environment to test the proposed model for viability.

KEYWORDS

Telecommunication, 3G networks, 4G Networks, Northwest Nigeria

For More Details: <http://airconline.com/ijcses/V10N1/10119ijcses01.pdf>

Volume Link: <http://aircse.org/journal/ijcses/current2019.html>

REFERENCES

- [1] N. C. Commission, "Subscriber statistics," Retrieved on 2nd February, 2018.
- [2] H. Gruber and P. Koutroumpis, "Mobile telecommunications and the impact on economic development," *Economic Policy*, vol. 26, no. 67, pp. 387-426, 2011.
- [3] K. M. Reilly and M. L. Smith, "**The emergence of open development in a network society**," *Open development: Networked innovations in international development*, pp. 15-50, 2013.
- [4] T. T. Alabar, O. Egena, and R. I. Gbande, "**Service quality and customer satisfaction in Nigerian mobile telephony**," *International Proceedings of Economics Development and Research*, vol. 82, p.108, 2014.
- [5] G. Intelligence, "**Sub-Saharan Africa Mobile Economy 2013**," See http://www.gsmamobileeconomyafrica.com/Sub-Saharan%20Africa_ME_Report_English_2013.pdf (last checked 19 September 2014), 2013.
- [6] J. Adewoye and T. Akanbi, "**Role of Information and Communication Technology Investment on the Profitability of Small Medium Scale Industries-A Case of Sachet Water Companies in Oyo State, Nigeria**," *Journal of Emerging Trends in Economics and Management Sciences*, vol. 3, no. 1, p. 64,2012.
- [7] E. Agwu and A.-L. Carter, "Mobile phone banking in Nigeria: benefits, problems and prospects,"2018.
- [8] A. Milek, C. Stork, and A. Gillwald, "Engendering communication: a perspective on ICT access and usage in Africa," *info*, vol. 13, no. 3, pp. 125-141, 2011.
- [9] K. Kumaravel, "**Comparative study of 3G and 4G in mobile technology**," *International Journal of Computer Science Issues (IJCSI)*, vol. 8, no. 5, p. 256, 2011.
- [10] K. Kumar, J. Liu, Y.-H. Lu, and B. Bhargava, "**A survey of computation offloading for mobile systems**," *Mobile Networks and Applications*, vol. 18, no. 1, pp. 129-140, 2013.
- [11] A. K. Mogal, "**Wireless mobile communication-a study of 3G technology**," *International Journal of Advanced Networking and Applications*, vol. 3, no. 5, p. 1, 2012.
- [12] P. Gigis, V. Kotronis, E. Aben, S. D. Strowes, and X. Dimitropoulos, "**Characterizing User-to-User Connectivity with RIPE Atlas**," in *Proceedings of the Applied Networking Research Workshop, 2017*,pp. 4-6: ACM.
- [13] J.-Y. Le Boudec and P. Thiran, **Network calculus: a theory of deterministic queuing systems for the internet**. Springer Science & Business Media, 2001.
- [14] B. Palanisamy and L. Liu, "**Attack-resilient mix-zones over road networks: architecture and algorithms**," *IEEE Transactions on Mobile Computing*, vol. 14, no. 3, pp. 495-508, 2015.
- [15] D. F. Mojisola and K. Gbolahan, "**Participatory Analysis of Cellular Network Quality of Service**," *International Journal of Computing & ICT Research*, vol. 9, no. 1, 2015.
- [16] R. Brenner et al., "**Development of Wireless Techniques in Data and Power Transmission-Application for Particle Physics Detectors**," arXiv preprint arXiv:1511.05807, 2015.
- [17] M. Poblet, "**Affordable telecommunications**," *Australian Journal of Telecommunications and the Digital Economy*, vol. 1, no. 1, 2013.
- [18] K.-D. Chang, C.-Y. Chang, H.-M. Liao, J.-L. Chen, and H.-C. Chao, "A Framework for IoT objects management based on future internet IoT-IMS communication platform," in *Innovative Mobile and Internet Services in Ubiquitous Computing (IMIS), 2013 Seventh International Conference on*, 2013, pp. 558-562: IEEE.

- [19] F. Ibikunle, O. Jakpa, and D. Ike, "Broadband Wireless Access Deployment Approach to Rural Communities," *Journal of Computer Networks*, vol. 1, no. 3, pp. 38-45, 2013.
- [20] W.-H. Sheen, S.-J. Lin, and C.-C. Huang, "Downlink optimization and performance of relay-assisted cellular networks in multicell environments," *IEEE Transactions on Vehicular Technology*, vol. 59, no. 5, pp. 2529-2542, 2010.
- [21] K. Santhi and G. S. Kumaran, "**WIMAX WITH WI-FI: OPENING NEW FRONTIERS IN EDUCATION.**"
- [22] J. Lambo, "Telecommunications-Nigeria," 2013.
- [23] S.-j. Kim, H. Lee, and M. Lee, "A Study of 4G Network for Security System," *The International Journal of Advanced Culture Technology*, vol. 3, no. 2, pp. 77-86, 2015.
- [24] A. Rusan and R. Vasiiu, "**Emulation of backhaul packet loss on the LTE S1-U interface and impact on end user throughput,**" in *Intelligent Computer Communication and Processing (ICCP)*, 2015 IEEE International Conference on, 2015, pp. 529-536: IEEE.
- [25] X. Zhang et al., "DSPP mutation in dentinogenesis imperfecta Shields type II," *Nature genetics*, vol. 27, no. 2, p. 151, 2001.
- [26] A. K. Salkintzis, "Wireless IP with GPRS: Fundamental operational aspects," in *4th Int. Symp. Wireless Personal Multimedia Communications*, 2001, pp. 7-15.

Automatic Facial Expression Analysis A Survey

C. P. Sumathi¹, T. Santhanam² and M. Mahadevi¹,

1SDNB Vaishnav College for Women, India and 2DG Vaishnav College for Men, India

ABSTRACT

The Automatic Facial Expression Recognition has been one of the latest research topic since 1990's. There have been recent advances in detecting face, facial expression recognition and classification. There are multiple methods devised for facial feature extraction which helps in identifying face and facial expressions. This paper surveys some of the published work since 2003 till date. Various methods are analysed to identify the Facial expression. The Paper also discusses about the facial parameterization using Facial Action Coding System(FACS) action units and the methods which recognizes the action units parameters using facial expression data that are extracted. Various kinds of facial expressions are present in human face which can be identified based on their geometric features, appearance features and hybrid features . The two basic concepts of extracting features are based on facial deformation and facial motion. This article also identifies the techniques based on the characteristics of expressions and classifies the suitable methods that can be implemented.

KEYWORDS

Facial Expression, FACS, Geometric Features, Appearance Features, Deformation, Facial Motion.

For More Details: <http://airccse.org/journal/ijcses/papers/3612ijcses04.pdf>

Volume Link: <http://airccse.org/journal/ijcses/current2012.html>

REFERENCES

- [1] G.Donato, M.S.Barlett, J.C.Hager, P.Keman, T.JSejnowski, "**Classifying Facial actions**", IEEE Trans.Pattern Analysis and Machine Intelligence,Vol.21 No.10 PP.974-989 ,1999.
- [2] P.Ekman and W.V.Friesen."Facial Action Coding System" .Consulting Pshychologists Press Inc.,577 College Avenue,Palo Alto,California 94306,1978.
- [3] A.Mehrabian ,"Communication without Words," Psychology Today ,Vol.2,no.4 ,pp.53-56,1968.
- [4] P. Dulguerov, F. Marchal, D. Wang, C. Gysin, P. Gidley, B.Gantz, J. Rubinstein, S. Sei7, L.Poon, K. Lun, Y. Ng, "**Review Of objective topographic facial nerve evaluation methods**", Am.J.Otol. 20 (5) (1999) 672–678.
- [5] J.Ostermann,"**Animation of synthetic faces in Mpeg-4**", Computer Animation, pp. 49-51,Philadelphia, Pennsylvania,June 8-10, 1998
- [6] B. Fasel,Juergen Luettin,"**Automatic facial expression analysis: a survey**, Pattern Recognition(2003) 259 – 275.
- [7] Maja Pantic, Student Member, IEEE, and Leon J.M. Rothkrantz, "**Automatic Analysis of Facial Expressions:The State of the Art**", IEEE Transactions on Pattern Analysis and Machine Intelligence, Vol. 22, No. 12, December 2000
- [8] Vinay Kumar Bettadapura, "**Face Expression Recognition and Analysis:The State of the Art**". College of Computing, Georgia Institute of Technology.
- [9] P.Ekman and W.V.Friesen , "Manual for the facial action coding system,"Consulting Psychologists Press,1977.
- [10] P. Ekman, W.V. Friesen, J.C. Hager, "Facial Action Coding System Investigator's Guide," A Human Face, Salt Lake City, UT, 2002.Consultant Pshchologists Press
- [11] Yingli Tian, Takeo Kanade and Jeffrey F. Cohn," **Recognizing Upper Face Action Units for Facial Expression Analysis**". Consultant Psychologists Press
- [12] Ying-li Tian , Takeo Kanade, Jeffrey F.Cohn," **Recognizing Lower Face Action Units for Facial Expression Analysis**". Consultant Psychologists Press
- [13] Anastasios C. Koutlas, Dimitrios I. Fotiadis "**A Region Based Methodology for facial expression recognition**." Systems, Man and Cybernetics, 2008. SMC 2008.
- [14] Ahmed Bilal Ashraf, Simon Lucey, Jeffrey F. Cohn, Tsuhan Chen, Zara Ambadar, Kenneth M. Prkachin,Patricia E. Solomon"**The painful face – Pain expression recognition using active appearance models**", Image and Vision Computing 27 (2009) 1788–1796
- [15] Maja Pantic,Ioanski Patras , "**Dynamics of facial expression and their temporal segments from face profile image sequences**". IEEE Transactions on Systems,Man and Cybernetics .
- [16] Jacob Whitehill ,Gwen Littlewort ,Ian Fasel,Marian Bartlett, Member IEEE,Javier Movellan. "**Toward Practical Smile Detection**" , IEEE Transactions on Pattern Analysis and Machine Intelligence , Vol 31.No11. November 2009.
- [17] Marian Stewart Bartlett,Gwen C.Littlewort , Mark.G.Frank,Claudia Lainscsek,Ian R.Fasel,Javier Movellan,"**Automatic Recognition of facial actions in spontaneous expressions**",Journal of Multimedia Vol 1,No.6 September 2006.

- [18] M.S.Bartlett,G.Littlewort,I.Fasel,J.R.Movellan, “**Real time face detection and expression recognition:Development and application to human-computer interaction**,Proceedings” .CVPR Workshop on computer vision and Pattern recognition for human-computer interaction
- [19] H.Rowley, S.Baluja, T.Kanade “**Neural Network based face detection**” ,IEEE Trans.Pattern Analysis and Machine Intelligence,Vol.20,no.1pp 23-28.
- [20] K.K.Sung & T.Poggio “**Example based learning for view based human face detection**”.IEEE Transactions Pattern analysis and machine intelligence,Vol.20,No.1 pp: 39-51
- [21] P.Viola,M.Jones .”**Robust real time face detection**”,Computer vision 2004,vol.57 no.2 pp 137- 154
- [22] P.Wang , Q.Ji “**Multiview face detection under complex scene based on combined SVMs**”,Proceedings IEEE International conference on Pattern recognition 2004,vol.4pp174-182
- [23] Mohammed Yeasin,Senior Member IEEE,Baptiste Bulot,Rajeev Sharma,Member IEEE “**Recognition of Facial Expressions and Measurement of Levels of Interest from video**”.IEEE Transactions on Multimedia Vol.8 No.3,June 2006
- [24] Yan Tong ,Yang Wang,Zhiwei Zhu,Qiang Ji ,”Robust Facial Feature Tracking under varying face pose and facial expression”,Pattern Recognition (40) 2007.
- [25] L. Wiskott, J.M. Fellous, N. Krüger, C.V. der Malsburg, “**Face recognition by elastic bunch graph matching**”, IEEE Trans. Pattern Anal. Mach. Intell. 19 (7) (1997) 775–779
- [26] Iodanis Mpiperis,Soteris Malassiotis and Michael G. Strintzis , “**Bilinear Models for 3D face and facial expression recognition**”.IEEE transactions on Information forensics and security.
- [27] Jun Wang,Lijun Yin,Xialozhou Wei and Yi sun, “**3D facial expression recognition based on primitive surface feature distribution.**” Department of Computer Science State University of New York at Binghamton
- [28] Tian, Y.-L., Brown, L., Hampapur, A., Pankanti, S., Senior, A., Bolle, R.: “**Real world realtime automatic recognition of facial expressions**”. In: Proceedings of IEEE Workshop on Performance Evaluation of Tracking and Surveillance, Graz, Austria (2003)
- [29] Maja Pantic,Leon J.M Rothkrantz ,”**Facial Action Recognition for Facial Expression Analysis from static face Images**” IEEE Transactions on System and Cybernetics Vol 34.No.3 2004.
- [30] Irane Kotsia and Ioannis Patras,Senior Member IEEE .” **Facial Expression Recognition in Image Sequences using Geometric Deformation Features and SVM**”, IEEE Transactions on Image Processing Vol16.No.1 January 2007.
- [31] Hong-Bo Deng ,Lian – Wen Jin ,Li-Xin Zhen, Jian –Cheng Huang, “**A New Facial Expression Recognition Method based on Local Gabor Filter Bank and PCA plus LDA**” . International Journal of Information Technology Vol. 11 No. 11 2005
- [32] S. Lucey, A. Ashraf, and J. Cohn, “**Investigating Spontaneous Facial Action Recognition through AAM Representations of the Face,**” Face Recognition, K. Delac and M. Grgic, eds., pp.275-286, I-Tech Education and Publishing, 2007.
- [33] C. Huang, Y. Huang,”Facial expression recognition using model-based feature extraction and action parameters classification”, J. Visual Commun. Image Representation 8 (3)1997.
- [34] Gabriele Fanelli, Angela Yao, Pierre-Luc Noel, Juergen Gall, and Luc Van Gool, “**Hough Forest-based Facial Expression Recognition from Video Sequences**”. International Workshop on Sign, Gesture and Activity (SGA) 2010, in conjunction with ECCV 2010.September 2010.

- [35] Pooja Sharma, Feature Based Method for “Human Facial Emotion Detection using optical Flow Based Analysis”, International Journal of Research in Computer Science eISSN 2249-8265 Volume 1 Issue 1 (2011) pp. 31-38
- [36] Sander Koelstra, Student Member, IEEE, Maja Pantic, Senior Member, IEEE, and Ioannis (Yiannis) Patras, Member, IEEE, “**A Dynamic Texture-Based Approach to Recognition of Facial Actions and Their Temporal Models**”, IEEE Transactions on Pattern Analysis and Machine Intelligence, Vol. 32, No. 11, November 2010
- [37] Devi Arumugam, Dr.S.Purushothaman, “**Emotion Classification using Facial Expression**” International Journal of Advanced Computer Science and Applications Vol.2 No.7, 2011
- [38] Shishir Bashyal,Ganesh k.Venayagamoorthy “Recognizing facial expressions using gabor wavelets and vector quantization”.Engineering Application of Artificial Intelligence(21) 2008.
- [39] Petar S.Aleksic,Member IEEE.Aggelos K.Katsaggelos,Fellow Member,IEEE,” Animation Parameters and Multistream HMM’s,IEEE Transactions on Information Forensics and Security”,Vol.1 No.1 March 2006.
- [40] Marian Stewart Bartlett, Gwen Littlewort , Mark Frank , Claudia Lainscek ,Ian Fasel ,Javier Movellan.”**Recognizing Facial Expression:Machine Learningand Application to Spontaneous Behavior** “Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition 2005
- [41] Peng Yang,Qingshan Liu,DimitrisN.Metaxas ,”Boosting Encoded dynamic features for facial Expression recognition”,Pattern Recognition Letters(30)2009.
- [42] Moriyama, T., Kanade, T., Cohn, J., Xiao, J., Ambadar, Z., Gao, J., Imanura, M.: “**Automatic recognition of eye blinking in spontaneously occurring behaviour**”. In: Proceedings of the 16th International Conference on Pattern Recognition (ICPR ’2002), vol. 4, pp. 78–81 (2002)
- [43] Xiao, J., Moriyama, T., Kanade, T., Cohn, J.: “**Robust full-motion recovery of head by dynamic templates and re-registration techniques**”. Int. J. Imaging Syst. Technol. (2003)
- [44] Le Hoang Thai, Nguyen Do Thai Nguyen and Tran Son Hai,member,IACSIT, “**A Facial Expression Classification System Integrating Canny, Principal Component Analysis and Artificial Neural Network**”,International Journal of Machine Learning and Computing, Vol. 1, No. 4, October 2011.
- [45] L. Ma and K. Khorasani “**Facial Expression Recognition Using Constructive Feedforward Neural Networks**”, IEEE Transactions on systems, man,and Cybernetics-Part B: Cybernetics, Vol. 34, No. 3, June 2004
- [46] Amir Jamshidnezhad, Md jan Nordin , “ **A Classifier Model based on the Features Quantitative Analysis for Facial Expression Recognition**” , Proceeding of the International Conference on Advanced Science, Engineering and Information Technology 2011
- [47] Maja Pantic and Ioannis Patras, “**Detecting Facial Actions and their Temporal Segments in Nearly Frontal-View Face Image Sequences**”, 2005 IEEE International Conference on Systems, Man and Cybernetics Waikoloa, Hawaii October 10-12, 2005
- [48] Yunfeng Zhu, Fernando De la Torre, Jeffrey F. Cohn, Associate Member, IEEE,and Yu-Jin Zhang, Senior Member, IEEE”**Dynamic Cascades with Bidirectional Bootstrapping for Action Unit Detection in Spontaneous Facial Behavior**”, Journal of LATEX Class Files, October 2010 .
- [49] Gwen C. Littlewort, Marian Stewart Bartlett, Kang Lee, “**Faces of Pain: Automated Measurement of Spontaneous Facial Expressions of Genuine and Posed Pain**”, ICMI’07, November 12–15, 2007, Nagoya, Aichi, Japan.

The Implication of Statistical Analysis and Feature Engineering for Model Building Using Machine Learning Algorithms

Swayanshu Shanti Pragnya and Shashwat Priyadarshi, Accenture, India

ABSTRACT

Scrutiny for presage is the era of advance statistics where accuracy matter the most. Commensurate between algorithms with statistical implementation provides better consequence in terms of accurate prediction by using data sets. Prolific usage of algorithms lead towards the simplification of mathematical models, which provide less manual calculations. Presage is the essence of data science and machine learning requisitions that impart control over situations. Implementation of any dogmas require proper feature extraction which helps in the proper model building that assist in precision. This paper is predominantly based on different statistical analysis which includes correlation significance and proper categorical data distribution using feature engineering technique that unravel accuracy of different models of machine learning algorithms.

KEYWORDS:

Correlation, Feature engineering, Feature selection, PCA, K nearest neighbour, logistic regression, RFE

For More Details: <http://airconline.com/ijcses/V10N3/10319ijcses01.pdf>

Volume Link: <http://aircse.org/journal/ijcses/current2019.html>

REFERENCES

- [1] GE, "Flight Quest Challenge," Kaggle.com. [Online]. Available: <https://www.kaggle.com/c/flight2-final>. [Accessed: 2-Jun-2017].
- [2] "Titanic: Machine Learning from Disaster," Kaggle.com. [Online]. Available: <https://www.kaggle.com/c/titanic>. [Accessed: 2-Jun-2017].
- [3] Wiki, "Titanic." [Online]. Available: <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Titanic..> [Accessed: 2-Jun-2017].
- [4] Kaggle, Data Science Community, [Online]. Available: <http://www.kaggle.com/> [Accessed: 2-Jun2017].
- [5] Multiple Regression, [Online] Available: <https://statistics.laerd.com/spss-tutorials/multipleregression-usingspss-statistics.php> [Accessed: 2-Jun-2017].
- [6] Logistic Regression, [Online] Available: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Logistic_regression [Accessed: 2-Jun2017].
- [7] Consumer Preferences to Specific Features in Mobile Phones: A Comparative Study [Online] Available: http://ermt.net/docs/papers/Volume_6/5_May2017/V6N5-107.pdf.
- [8] Multiple Linear Regression, [Online] Available <http://www.statisticssolutions.com/assumptions-ofmultiplelinear-regression/> [Accessed: 3-Jun-2017]
- [9] Prediction of Survivors in Titanic Dataset: A Comparative Study using Machine Learning Algorithms Tryambak Chatterjee* Department of Management Studies, NIT Trichy, Tiruchirappalli, Tamilnadu, India

A Survey on Internal Validity Measure for Cluster Validation

L.Jegatha Deborah, R.Baskaran and A.Kannan ,

Anna University – Chennai

ABSTRACT

Data Clustering is a technique of finding similar characteristics among the data set which are always hidden in nature and grouping them into groups, called as clusters. Different clustering algorithms exhibit different results, since they are very sensitive to the characteristics of original data set especially noise and dimension. The quality of such clustering process determines the purity of cluster and hence it is very important to evaluate the results of the clustering algorithm. Due to this, Cluster validation activity had been a major and challenging task. The major factor which influences cluster validation is the internal cluster validity measure of choosing the optimal number of clusters. The main objective of this article is to present a detailed description of the mathematical working of few cluster validity indices and not all, to classify these indices and to explore the ideas for the future promotion of the work in the domain of cluster validation. In addition to this, a maximization objective function is defined assuming to provide a cluster validation activity.

KEYWORDS:

Data clustering, cluster, cluster purity, cluster analysis, cluster validation, cluster validity indices.

For More Details: <http://airccse.org/journal/ijcses/papers/1110ijcses07.pdf>

Volume Link: <http://airccse.org/journal/ijcses/currentissue.html>

REFERENCES

1. James C. Bezdek, Fellow, IEEE, and Nikhil R. Pal, (1998) "Some New Indexes of Cluster Validity", IEEE transactions on Systems, Man, and Cybernetics—Part b: Cybernetics, vol. 28, no. 3.
2. http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Convex_hull.
3. J. C. Bezdek, W. Q. Li, Y. Attikiouzel, and M. Windham,(1997) "A geometric approach to cluster validity for normal mixtures," Journal on Soft Computing – A Fusion of Foundations, Methodologies and Applications, vol. 1, no.4, 166–179.
4. A. Jain and R. Dubes, (1998) "**Algorithms for Clustering Data**", Englewood Cliffs, NJ: Prentice Hall.
5. Maria Halkidi Michalis Vazirgiannis, (2001) "**Clustering Validity Assessment: Finding the optimal partitioning of a data set**", First IEEE International Conference on Data Mining (ICDM'01).
6. Rakesh Agrawal, Johannes Gehrke, Dimitrios Gunopulos, Prabhakar Raghavan,(1998) "**Automatic Subspace Clustering of High Dimensional Data for Data Mining Applications**". Proceedings of ACM SIGMOD, vol. 27, Issue 2.
7. Alexander Hinneburg, Daniel Keim, (1998) "**An Efficient Approach to Clustering in Large Multimedia Databases with Noise**". Proceeding of KDD '98.
8. Ujjwal Maulik, Sanghamitra Bandyopadhyay, (2002) "**Performance Evaluation of Some Clustering Algorithms and Validity Indices**", IEEE Transactions on Pattern Analysis And Machine Intelligence, Vol. 24, No. 12.
9. L.O. Hall, I.B. Ozyurt, and J. C. Bezdek, (1999) "**Clustering with a Genetically Optimized Approach**," IEEE Transactions on Evolutionary Computation, vol. 3, no. 2,103-112.
10. R.B. Calinski and J. Harabasz, (1974) "A Dendrite Method for Cluster Analysis," Communication in Statistics – Simulation and Computation, Vol. 3, Issue 1, 1-27.
11. Minho Kim, R.S. Ramakrishna, (2005) "New indices for cluster validity assessment", Elsevier Journal on Pattern Recognition Letters 26, 2353–2363.
12. Berry, M.J.A., Linoff, G., (1997) "**Data Mining Techniques: For Marketing, Sales, and Customer Support**", John Wiley & Sons, Berlin.
13. Kadim Tas,demir and Erzs'ebet Mer'enyi, (2007) "**A new cluster validity index for prototype based clustering algorithms based on inter- and intra-cluster density**", In Proceedings of International Joint Conference on Neural Networks, 2007 (IJCNN 2007), Orlando, FL.
14. K.L Wu, and M.S. Yang, "**A cluster validity index for fuzzy clustering,(2005)** "ElSevier Journal on Pattern Recognition Letters, vol. 26, Issue 9, 1275–1291.
15. U. Maulik, and S. Bandyopadhyay, (2002) "**Performance evaluation of some clustering algorithms and validity indices**," IEEE Transactions on Pattern Analysis and Machine Intelligence, vol. 24, no. 12.
16. X.L. Xie, and G. Beni, (1991) "**A validity measure for fuzzy clustering**," IEEE Transactions on Pattern Analysis and Machine Intelligence, Vol.13, no.8, pp.841–847.
17. Chang Wook Ahn and R.S. Ramakrishna, (2002) "**A Genetic Algorithm for Shortest Path Routing Problem and the Sizing of Populations**", IEEE Transactions on Evolutionary Computation, Vol.6, No.6.
18. Sanghoun Oh, Chang Wook Ahn, Moongu Jeon, (2008), "An Evolutionary Cluster Validation Index", Proceedings of 3rd International Conference on Bio- Inspired Computing: Theories and Applications, BICTA 2008, 83-88.

19. Nam Hyun Park, Chang Wook Ahn, and R.S. Ramakrishna, (2005) "Adaptive Clustering Technique Using Genetic Algorithms", IEICE Transactions on Information and System, Vol.E88-D. No.12.
20. C.-H Chou, M.-C. Su, and E. Lai, (2006) "A new cluster validity measure and its application to image Compression Sergios Theodoridis", Pattern Recognition (Third Edition), Academic Press, Inc. Orlando, FL, USA.
21. Sriparna Saha and Sanghamitra Bandyopadhyay, (2009) "A Validity Index Based on Connectivity", Seventh International Conference on Advances in Pattern Recognition.
22. C. H. Chou, M. C. Su, and E. Lai, (2004) "**A new cluster validity measure and its application to image compression**," ACM Journal on Pattern Analysis and Applications, vol. 7, Issue 2, 205–220.
23. S. Bandyopadhyay and S. Saha, (2008) "**A point symmetry based clustering technique for automatic evolution of clusters**," IEEE Transactions on Knowledge and Data Engineering, vol. 20, no. 11, 1–17.
24. S. Saha and S. Bandyopadhyay, (2008) "**Application of a new symmetry based cluster validity index for satellite image segmentation**," IEEE Geoscience and Remote Sensing Letters, vol. 5, no. 2, 166–170.
25. Deng Ying, Yang Shuangyuan, and Liu Han, (2009) "A Subtractive Based Subspace Clustering Algorithm on High Dimensional Data", Proceedings of the 1st International Conference on Information Science and Engineering (ICISE2009).
26. H. Sun and M. Sun, (2006) "Trail-and-error approach for determining the number of clusters"[J]. ICMLC 2005, LNAI 3930, vol. 3930, 229 – 238.
27. Lifei Chen, Qingshan Jiang, Shengrui Wang, (2008) "Cluster validation for subspace clustering on high dimensional data" [C], Proceeding of the 2008 IEEE Asia Pacific Conference on Circuits and Systems, Macao:China.
28. L.Jing, M.K.Ng and J.Z.Huang, (2007) "An entropy weighting k-means algorithm for subspace clustering of high-dimensional sparse data"[J]. IEEE Transactions on Knowledge and Data Engineering, vol.19, no.8, 1-16.
29. C.Domeniconi, D.Gunopulos, et al. (2007) "**Locally adaptive metrics for clustering high dimensional data**", ACM Journal on Data Mining and Knowledge Discovery, vol 14, Issue 1.
30. Zhiling Hong, Qingshan Jiang, Huailin Dong and Shengrui Wang. (2008) "A new cluster validity index for fuzzy clustering", Elsevier Journal on Information Sciences, vol. 178, Issue 4.
31. S.M. Pan and K.-S. Cheng, (2007) "**Evolution-based tabu search approach to automatic clustering**," IEEE Transactions on Systems, Man, and Cybernetics. C, Appl. Rev., vol. 37, no. 5, 827–838.
32. E. Hruschka, R. J. G. B. Campello, A. A. Freitas, and A. C. Ponce Leon F. de Carvalho, (2009) "**A survey of evolutionary algorithms for clustering**," IEEE Transactions on Systems, Man, and Cybernetics. C, Appl. Rev., vol. 39, no. 2, 133–155.
33. U.Maulik, (2008) "Hierarchical pattern discovery in graphs," IEEE Transactions on Systems, Man, and Cybernetics C, Appl. Rev., vol. 38, no. 6, 867–872 .

A Study of Techniques for Facial Detection and Expression Classification

G.Hemalatha¹ and C.P. Sumathi²,

¹Manonmaniam Sundaranar University, India and ²SDNB Vaishnav College for Women, India

ABSTRACT

Automatic recognition of facial expressions is an important component for human-machine interfaces. It has lot of attraction in research area since 1990's. Although humans recognize face without effort or delay, recognition by a machine is still a challenge. Some of its challenges are highly dynamic in their orientation, lightening, scale, facial expression and occlusion. Applications are in the fields like user authentication, person identification, video surveillance, information security, data privacy etc. The various approaches for facial recognition are categorized into two namely holistic based facial recognition and feature based facial recognition. Holistic based treat the image data as one entity without isolating different region in the face where as feature based methods identify certain points on the face such as eyes, nose and mouth etc. In this paper, facial expression recognition is analyzed with various methods of facial detection, facial feature extraction and classification.

KEYWORDS

Face detection, Feature extraction, Machine learning, Classification, Expression recognition.

For More Details: <http://airccse.org/journal/ijcses/papers/5214ijcses03.pdf>

Volume Link: <http://airccse.org/journal/ijcses/current2014.html>

REFERENCES

- [1] Beehara, A. H.Damasio and A.R.Damasio, (2000)“ **Emotion Decision making and orbit frontal cortex**, 10(3): p 295-307.
- [2] Ekman, P.Friesen ”Facial Action Coding System”,PaloAlto, CA,:Consulting Physiologists press,1978.
- [3] Ming-Husan Yang,David J.Kriegman,Narendra Ahuja ,”**Detecting Faces in Images:A survey**” IEEE Transaction on Pattern Analysis and Machine Intelligence”,Vol.24,No.1,Jan 2002.
- [4] Rajesh A Patil, Vineet Sabula, A.S.Mandal “**Automatic Detection of Facial Feature Points in Image sequences**”, 978-1-61284-861-7/11 IEEE 2011
- [5] W. Kienzle, G. BakIr, M. Franz, and B. Scholkopf, "**Face detection- efficient and rank deficient**:" in Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems, vol. 17, pp. 673-t>80, 2005.
- [6] P. Viola and M. Jones, "**Robust real-time object detection**:" in International Journal of Computer Vision, 2001.
- [7] T. Kanade, J. Cohn, and Y. Tian, "**Comprehensive database for facial expression analysis**:" in Fourth IEEE International Conference on Automatic Face and Gesture Recognition, pp. 46 -53, 2000.
- [8] Yu-Buhee and Sukhanlee " ETRI Journal, Volume 33,No.4,August 2011.
- [9] Yow and Cipolla "**Feature Based Human Face Detection**" Image and Vision Computing vol15,No.9 pp 713-735,1997.
- [10] A.Punitha, M.Kalaiselvigeetha "**Texture based Emotion Recognition from Facial Expression using Support Vector Machine**" International Journal of Computer Applications(0975-8887) Vol 80, No.5,October 2013.
- [11] Sanjay Kr.singh,D.S.Chauhan,Mayank Vatsa,Richa Singh "**A robust Skin Color Based Face Detection Algorithm**" Tamkang Journal of Science and Engineering, Vol 6,No4,pp227-234(2003).
- [12] Jiaming Li, Geoff Poulton, Ying Guo,Rong-Yu Qiao "**Face Recognition Based on Multiple Region Features**" Proc.VIIth Digital Image Computing:Techniques and Applications,Sunc,Talbot H,OurselinS. and Adriaansen T.(Eds), 10-12 Dec 2003,Sydney.
- [13] Caifeng shan,Shaogang Gong,Peter W,Mcowan "**Facial expression recognition based on Local Binary Patterns: A comprehensive Study**" Image and Vision Computing 27(2009) 803-816.
- [14] Rajesh A.Patil, Vineet Sahula and A.S.Mandal "Facial Expression Recognition in Image sequences using Active Shape Model and Support Vector Machine" 2011 UKSIM 5th European Symposium on Computer Modeling and Simulation.
- [15] Yogesh Tayal, Pramod Pandey,D.B.V.Singh "Face Recognition using Eigenface" International Journal of Emerging Technologies in Computational and Applied Sciences (IJETCAS) 3 (1), Dec.12-Feb., 2013, pp. 50-55
- [16] Jeemoni Kalita , Karen Das "**Recognition of Facial Expression Using Eigenvector Based Distributed Features and Euclidean Distance Based Decision Making Technique**" (IJACSA) International Journal of Advanced Computer Science and Applications, Vol.4, No.2, 2013.
- [17] Sandeep K. Gupta, ShubhLakshmi Agrwal, Yogesh K. Meena, Neeta Nain "A Hybrid Method of Feature Extraction for Facial Expression Recognition" 2011 Seventh International Conference on Signal Image Technology & Internet-Based Systems.
- [18] Ziyang Zhang, Xiaomin Mu, Lei Gao " **Recognizing Facial Expressions Based on Gabor Filter Selection**" 2011 4th International Congress on Image and Signal Processing.
- [19] Zhiguo Niu ,Prof. Xuehong Qiu "Facial Expression Recognition based on weighted principal component analysis andsupport vector machines" 2010 3rd International Conference on Advanced Computer Theory and Engineering (ICACTE).

- [20] Marian Stewart Bartlett [Member, IEEE], Javier R. Movellan [Member, IEEE], and Terrence J. Sejnowski [Fellow, IEEE] " Face Recognition by Independent Component Analysis" IEEE Trans Neural Netw. 2002 ; 13(6): 1450–1464.
- [21] Li-Fen Chen, Hong-Yuan Mark Liao, Ming-Tat Ko, Ja-Chen Lin, Gwo-Jong Yu " **A new LDA-based face recognition system which can solve the small sample size problem**" Pattern Recognition 33 (2000)1713-1726.
- [22] Teik-Toe TEOH Siu-Yeung CHO "Human Emotional States Modeling by Hidden Markov Model" 2011 Seventh International Conference on Natural Computation.
- [23] Er. Monika Verma Er. Pooja Rani Er. Harish Kundra **A Hybrid Approach to Human Face Detection 2010** International Journal of Computer Applications(0975-8887)Vol 1-No.13.
- [24] Gwen Littlewort, Marian Stewart Bartlett "**Dynamics of facial expression extracted automatically from video**" Image and Vision Computing 24(2006) 615-625
- [25] Chin-Shyurng Fahn, Ming-Hui Wu, Chang Yi Kao "**Real-time Facial Expression Recognition in Image Sequences using an AdaBoost based Multiclassifier**" Proceedings of 2009 APSIPA Annual Summit and Conference, Sapporo, Japan, October 4-7, 2009.
- [26] Hiroshi Kobayashi and Fuimio Haro "Analysis of Neural Network Recognition characteristics at Basic Facial Expression" IEEE International Workshop on Robot and Human Communication 0-7803-2002-6/94, 1994 IEEE
- [27] Chung-Lin Huang and Yu-Ming Huang " Facial Expression Recognition Using Model-Based Feature Extraction" Vol. 8, No. 3, September, pp. 278–290, 1997.
- [28] Beat Fasel, IDIAP, Martigny "Head Pose invariant Facial Expression Recognition using Convolutional Neural Network" Fourth IEEE International Conference on Multimodal Interfaces 0-7695-1834-6/02 © 2002 IEEE.
- [29] Khalid, Fatimah, Tengku Mod, Omar, Khiruddin "Face Expression Recognition with Relevance Vector Machine" ICME (Multi media & Expo) IEEE International Conference Pg 193-196 24th Oct 2005.
- [30] Aleksic P.S, Katsaggelos, "**Automatic facial expression recognition using facial animation parameters and multi stream HMMS**", Vol 1 Issue: 1 Pg No: 3-11 March 2006 IEEE Signal Processing Society.
- [31] Pritpal Dang, Harry Stephanou, Fredric Ham, Frank . L Lewis, " Facial Expression Recognition using a Two Stage Neural Network", I-4244-1282--X107 © 2007 IEEE July 27-29 Althene – Greece.
- [32] Govind U Kharat & Sanjay V Dida, " Emotion Recognition from Facial Expression Using Neural Network" I-4244-1543-8/08 © 2008 IEEE.
- [33] Kazmil S.B. Qurat - ul - Ain, Ishiag. M, Jaffar M.A, " Texture analysis based facial expression recognition using a Bayesian classifiers", ICIET 2010 Pg No 1-6 9 Nov 2010.
- [34] Jiequan Li, Oussalah M, "Automatic Face emotion recognition system" Cybernet Intelligent Systems (CIS) 2010 IEEE 9th International Conference Vol 1, Pg 1-6.
- [35] Anissa Bouzalmat, Naouar Beghini, Arsalane Zarghili, Jamal Kharroubi, "**Face detection and Recognition using base propagation Neural Network and Fourier Gabor Filters**" SIPIJ Vol 2, No.3 Sep 2011.
- [36] Boughrara.H; Liming, chen; Ben Amar.C, Chtourou.M, " Face Recognition under varying Facial Expression based on Perceived Facial images and Local Feature matching "2012 International Conference on Information Technology and e Services, Pg 24-26 Mar 2012.
- [37] Rahulmathavan Y; Phan R.D.-W; Chambers, J.A; Parish.D.J, "Facial Expression Recognition in the Encrypted Domain Based on Local Fisher Discriminant Analysis" Affective Computing, IEEE Transaction on vol 4; issue 1, Jan-Mar 2013.
- [38] Dileep M.R, Aijit Danti, "**Lines of Connectivity-Face Model for Recognition of the Human Facial Expressions**" International Journal of Artificial Intelligence and Mechatronics Vol2, Issue2 , ISSN 2320-5121.

Software Testing Using Genetic Algorithms

Akshat Sharma, Rishon Patani and Ashish Aggarwal,
VIT University, India

ABSTRACT

This paper presents a set of methods that uses a genetic algorithm for automatic test-data generation in software testing. For several years researchers have proposed several methods for generating test data which had different drawbacks. In this paper, we have presented various Genetic Algorithm (GA) based test methods which will be having different parameters to automate the structural-oriented test data generation on the basis of internal program structure. The factors discovered are used in evaluating the fitness function of Genetic algorithm for selecting the best possible Test method. These methods take the test populations as an input and then evaluate the test cases for that program. This integration will help in improving the overall performance of genetic algorithm in search space exploration and exploitation fields with better convergence rate.

KEYWORDS

Genetic algorithm, Fitness function, Test data.

For More Details: <http://airconline.com/ijcses/V7N2/7216ijcses03.pdf>

Volume Link: <http://aircse.org/journal/ijcses/current2016.html>

REFERENCES

- [1] Goldberg, D.E, “**Genetic Algorithms: in Search, Optimization & Machine Learning**,” Addison Wesley, MA. 1989.
- [2] Horgan, J., London, S., and Lyu, M., “Achieving Software Quality with Testing Coverage Measures”, IEEE Computer, Vol. 27 No.9 pp. 60-69, 1994.
- [3] Berndt, D.J., Fisher, J., Johnson, L., Pinglikar, J., and Watkins, A., “**Breeding Software Test Cases with Genetic Algorithms**,” In Proceedings of the Thirty-Sixth Hawaii International Conference on System Sciences HICSS-36), Hawaii, January 2003.
- [4] Mark Last, Shay Eyal, and Abraham Kandel, “**Effective Black-Box Testing with Genetic Algorithms**,” IBM conference.
- [5] Lin, J.C. and Yeh, P.L, “Using Genetic Algorithms for Test Case Generation in Path Testing,” In Proceedings of the 9th Asian Test Symposium (ATS’00). Taipei, Taiwan, December 4-6, 2000.
- [6] André Baresel, Harmen Sthamer and Michael Schmidt, “**fitness function design to improve evolutionary structural testing**,” proceedings of the genetic and evolutionary computation conference, 2002.
- [7] Christoph C. Michael, Gary E. McGraw, Michael A. Schatz, and Curtis C. Walton, “**Genetic Algorithms for Dynamic Test Data Generation**,” Proceedings of the 1997 International Conference on Automated Software Engineering (ASE’97) (formerly: KBSE) 0-8186-7961-1/97 © 1997 IEEE.
- [8] Somerville, I., “Software engineering,” 7th Ed. Addison-Wesley,
- [9] Aditya P mathur, “Foundation of Software Testing”, 1st edition Pearson Education 2008.
- [10] Alander, J.T., Mantere, T., and Turunen, P, “Genetic Algorithm Based Software Testing,” <http://citeseer.ist.psu.edu/40769.html>, 1997.
- [11] Nashat Mansour, Miran Salame, “Data Generation for Path Testing”, Software Quality Journal, 12, 121–136, 2004, Kluwer Academic Publishers.
- [12] Praveen Ranjan Srivastava et al, “Generation of test data using Meta heuristic approach” IEEE TENCON (19-21 NOV 2008), India available in IEEEEXPLORE.
- [13] Wegener, J., Baresel, A., and Sthamer, H, “Suitability of Evolutionary Algorithms for Evolutionary Testing,” In Proceedings of the 26th Annual International Computer Software and Applications Conference, Oxford, England, August 26-29, 2002.
- [14] Berndt, D.J. and Watkins A, “Investigating the Performance of Genetic Algorithm-Based. Software Test Case Generation,” In Proceedings of the Eighth IEEE International Symposium on High Assurance Systems Engineering (HASE’04), pp. 261-262, University of South Florida, March 25-26, 2004.
- [15] B. Korel. **Automated software test data generation**. IEEE Transactions on Software Engineering, 16(8), August 1990.
- [16] Bo Zhang, Chen Wang, “Automatic generation of test data for path testing by adaptive genetic simulated annealing algorithm”, IEEE, 2011, pp. 38 – 42.
- [17] Chartchai Doungsa et. al., “**An automatic test data generation from UML state diagram using genetic algorithm**”, <http://eastwest.inf.brad.ac.uk/document/publication/DoungsaardSKIMA.pdf>.
- [18] D.J Berndt, A. Watkins, “High volume software testing using genetic algorithms”, Proceedings of the 38th International Conference on system sciences (9), IEEE, 2005, pp. 1- 9.
- [19] Francisca Emanuelle et. al., “**Using Genetic algorithms for test plans for functional testing**”, 44th ACM SE proceeding, 2006, pp. 140 - 145.

- [20] Goldberg, D.E, **Genetic Algorithms: in search, optimization and machine learning**, Addison Wesley, M.A, 1989.
- [21] Girgis, “**Automatic test generation for data flow testing using a genetic algorithm**”, Journal of computer science, 11 (6), 2005, pp. 898 – 915.
- [22] Giuseppe A. et. al., “**Testing Web –applications: The State of Art and Future Trends**”.Information and Software Technology. Elsevier, 2006, pp. 1172-1186.
- [23] Jin- Cherng Lin, Pu- Lin Yeh, “Automatic test data generation for path testing using Gas”, International journal of information sciences. Elsevier, 2000, pp. 47- 64.
- [24] Jose Carlos et. al., “**A strategy for evaluating feasible and unfeasible test cases for the evolutionary testing of object-oriented software**”, AST’ 08. ACM, 2008, http://www.cs.bham.ac.uk/~wbl/biblio/cache/http___jcbri_beiro.googlepages.com_ast12-ribeiro.pdf, Accessed on 6.11.2012.
- [25] Liang You, YanSheng Lu, “A genetic algorithm for the time – aware regression testing reduction problem”, International conference on natural computation, IEEE, 2012, pp. 596 – 599.
- [26] McMinn, “**Search based software test generation: A survey**”, Software testing, Verification and reliability 14 (2), 2004, pp. 105-156.
- [27] Mark Last et. al., “**Effective black-box testing with genetic algorithms**”, Lecture notes in computer science, Springer, 2006, pp. 134 -148.
- [28] Maha alzabidi et. al., “**Automatic software structural testing by using evolutionary algorithms for test data generations**”, International Journal of Computer science and Network Security 9 (4), 2009, pp.390 – 395.
- [29] Velur Rajappa et. al., “Efficient software test case generation Using genetic algorithm based graph theory” International conference on emerging trends in Engineering and Technology, IEEE, 2008, pp.298 - 303.
- [30] Xuan Peng, Lu Lu, “A new approach for session - based test case generation by GA”. IEEE, 2011, pp.91-96.
- [31] Peter M. Kruse et. al., “A Highly Configurable test systems for evolutionary black box testing of embedded systems” GECCO. ACM, 2009, pp.1545 – 1551.
- [32] Ruilian zhao, shanshan lv, “Neural network based test cases generation using genetic algorithm” 13th IEEE international symposium on Pacific Rim dependable computing. IEEE, 2007, pp.97 - 100.
- [33] Robert M .Patton et. al. “**A genetic algorithm approach to focused software usage testing**” **Annals of software engineering**,<http://www.cs.ucf.edu/~ecl/papers/03.rmpatton.pdf>.

Sign Language Converter

Taner Arsan and Oğuz

Ülgen, Kadir Has University, Turkey

ABSTRACT

The aim of this paper is to design a convenient system that is helpful for the people who have hearing difficulties and in general who use very simple and effective method; sign language. This system can be used for converting sign language to voice and also voice to sign language. A motion capture system is used for sign language conversion and a voice recognition system for voice conversion. It captures the signs and dictates on the screen as writing. It also captures the voice and displays the sign language meaning on the screen as motioned image or video.

KEYWORDS

Motion Capture, Motioned Image, Sign Language Converter, Voice Recognition.

For More Details: <http://airccse.org/journal/ijcses/papers/6415ijcses03.pdf>

Volume Link: <http://airccse.org/journal/ijcses/current2015.html>

REFERENCES

- [1] J.P. Bonet. "Reduccion de las letras y arte para enseñar a hablar a los mudos", Coleccion Clasicos Pepe. C.E.P.E., 1992.
- [2] William C. Stokoe. Sign Language Structure [microform] / William C. Stokoe. Distributed by ERIC Clearinghouse, [Washington, D.C.], 1978.
- [3] William C. Stokoe, Dorothy C Casterline, and Carl G Croneberg. "A Dictionary of American Sign Language on Linguistic Principles" Linstok Press, [Silver Spring, Md.], New Edition, 1976.
- [4] Code Laboratories. CL NUI Platform. <http://codelaboratories.com/ kb/nui>
- [5] The Robot Operating System (ROS), <http://www.ros.org/wiki/ kinect>.
- [6] Open Kinect Project, http://openkinect.org/wiki/Main_Page.
- [7] Open NI API Reference. <http://openni.org/Documentation/Reference/ index.html>.
- [8] Bridle, J., Deng, L., Picone, J., Richards, H., Ma, J., Kamm, T., Schuster, M., Pike, S., Reagan, R., "**An Investigation of Segmental Hidden Dynamic Models of Speech co-articulation for Automatic Speech Recognition**.", Final Report for the 1998 Workshop on Language Engineering, Center for Language and Speech Processing at Johns Hopkins University, pp. 161, 1998.
- [9] Ma, J., Deng, L., "**Target-directed Mixture Linear Dynamic Models for Spontaneous Speech Recognition**", IEEE Transactions on Speech and Audio Processing, Vol. 12, No. 1, January 2004.
- [10] Ma, J., Deng, L., "**A Mixed-level Switching Dynamic System for Continuous Speech Recognition**", Elsevier Computer Speech and Language 18 (2004) 4965, 2004.
- [11] Mori R.D, Lam L., Gilloux M., "Learning & Plan Refinement in a Knowledge Based System for Automatic Speech Recognition", IEEE Tra. on Pattern Analysis Machine Int., 9(2):289-305, 1987.
- [12] Rabiner, L., R., and Wilpon, J. G., "Considerations in Applying Clustering Techniques to Speakerindependent Word Recognition", Journal of Acoustic Society of America, 66 (3):663-673, 1979.
- [13] Tolba, H., and O'Shaughnessy, D., "**Speech Recognition by Intelligent Machines**", IEEE Canadian Review (38), 2001.
- [14] Kathryn LaBelle, "Kinect Rehabilitation Project", <http://netscale.cse.nd.edu/twiki/bin/view/Edu/KinectRehabilitation>, June 2009.

Complete Synchronization of Hyperchaotic Xu and Hyperchaotic Lu Systems via Active Control

Sundarapandian Vaidyanathan,

Vel Tech Dr. RR & Dr. SR Technical University, India

ABSTRACT

This paper deploys active control for achieving complete synchronization of hyperchaotic Xu (2009) and hyperchaotic Lü (2006) systems. Specifically, this paper derives complete synchronization results for identical hyperchaotic Xu systems, identical hyperchaotic Lü systems and non-identical hyperchaotic Xu and Lü systems. The complete synchronization results have been proved using Lyapunov stability theory. Numerical simulations have been shown to validate and demonstrate the effectiveness of the complete synchronization results derived in this paper.

KEYWORDS

Active Control, Synchronization, Hyperchaos, Hyperchaotic Xu System, Hyperchaotic Lü System.

For More Details: <http://airccse.org/journal/ijcses/papers/3312ijcses03.pdf>

Volume Link: <http://airccse.org/journal/ijcses/current2012.html>

REFERENCES

- [1] Lorenz, E.N. (1963) "**Deterministic nonperiodic flow**", J. Atmos. Sci., Vol. 20, pp 130-141.
- [2] Lakshmanan, M. & Murali, K. (1996) Nonlinear Oscillators: Controlling and Synchronization, World Scientific, Singapore.
- [3] Han, S.K., Kerrer, C. & Kuramoto, Y. (1995) "**Dephasing and bursting in coupled neural oscillators**", Phys. Rev. Lett., Vol. 75, pp 3190-3193.
- [4] Blasius, B., Huppert, A. & Stone, L. (1999) "**Complex dynamics and phase synchronization in spatially extended ecological system**", Nature, Vol. 399, pp 354-359.
- [5] Feki, M. (2003) "**An adaptive chaos synchronization scheme applied to secure communication**", Chaos, Solitons and Fractals, Vol. 18, pp 141-148.
- [6] Murali, K. & Lakshmanan, M. (1998) "Secure communication using a compound signal from generalized synchronizable chaotic systems", Phys. Rev. Lett. A, Vol. 241, pp 303-310.
- [7] Pecora, L.M. & Carroll, T.L. (1990) "**Synchronization in chaotic systems**", Phys. Rev. Lett., Vol. 64, pp 821-824.
- [8] Ott, E., Grebogi, C. & Yorke, J.A. (1990) "**Controlling chaos**", Phys. Rev. Lett., Vol. 64, pp 1196-1199.
- [9] Ho, M.C. & Hung, Y.C. (2002) "Synchronization of two different chaotic systems by using generalized active control", Physics Letters A, Vol. 301, pp. 424-428.
- [10] Chen, H.K. (2005) "Global chaos synchronization of new chaotic systems via nonlinear control", Chaos, Solitons & Fractals, Vol. 23, pp. 1245-1251.
- [11] Sundarapandian, V. & Rasappan, S. (2010) "Global chaos synchronization of Newton-Leipnik system and Liu-Chen four scroll chaotic attractor by nonlinear control," International Journal of Control Theory and Applications, Vol. 3, No. 1, pp 29-36.
- [12] Sundarapandian, V. (2011) "**Global chaos synchronization of four-scroll and four-wing chaotic attractors by active nonlinear control**," International Journal on Computer Science and Engineering, Vol. 3, No. 5, pp 2145-2155.
- [13] Sundarapandian, V. (2011) "**Anti-synchronization of Arneodo and Coulet systems by active nonlinear control**," International Journal of Control Theory and Applications, Vol. 4, No. 1, pp 25-36.
- [14] Liao, T.L. & Tsai, S.H. (2000) "**Adaptive synchronization of chaotic systems and its applications to secure communications**", Chaos, Solitons and Fractals, Vol. 11, pp 1387-1396.
- [15] Sundarapandian, V. (2011) "**Adaptive control and synchronization of hyperchaotic Cai system**", International Journal of Control Theory and Computer Modelling, Vol. 1, No. 1, pp. 1-13.
- [16] Sundarapandian, V. (2011) "Adaptive synchronization of hyperchaotic Lorenz and hyperchaotic Liu systems", International Journal of Instrumentation and Control Systems, Vol. 1, No. 1, pp. 1-18.
- [17] Sundarapandian, V. (2011) "**Adaptive control and synchronization of a highly chaotic attractor**," International Journal of Information Sciences and Techniques, Vol. 1, No. 2, pp 1-11.
- [18] Tan, X., Zhang, J. & Yang, Y. (2003) "Synchronizing chaotic systems using backstepping design," Chaos, Solitons & Fractals, Vol. 16, pp 37-45.
- [19] Yu, Y.G. & Zhang, S.C. (2006) "Adaptive backstepping synchronization of uncertain chaotic systems", Chaos, Solitons & Fractals, Vol. 27, pp 1369-1375.

- [20] Laoye, J.A., Vincent, U.E. & Kareem, S.O. (2009) "Chaos control of 4-D chaotic system using recursive backstepping nonlinear controller," *Chaos, Solitons & Fractals*, Vol. 39, pp 356-362.
- [21] Yang, T. & Chua, L.O. (1999) "**Control of chaos using sampled-data feedback control**", *Internat. J. Bifurcat. Chaos*, Vol. 9, pp 215-219.
- [22] Sundarapandian, V. (2011) "Global chaos synchronization of four-wing chaotic systems by sliding mode control", *International Journal of Control Theory and Computer Modelling*, Vol. 1, No. 1, pp. 15-31.
- [23] Sundarapandian, V. (2011) "**Global chaos synchronization of Pehlivan systems by sliding mode control**", *International Journal on Computer Science and Engineering*, Vol. 3, No. 5, pp. 2163- 2169.
- [24] Sundarapandian, V. (2011) "**Sliding mode controller design for the synchronization of ShimizuMorioka chaotic systems**", *International Journal of Information Sciences and Techniques*, Vol. 1, No. 1, pp 20-29.
- [25] Sundarapandian, V. (2011) "Hybrid synchronization of hyperchaotic Newton-Leipnik systems via sliding mode control," *International Journal of Control Theory and Computer Modelling*, Vol. 1, No. 2, pp 1-10.
- [26] Sundarapandian, V. (2012) "**Anti-synchronization of Pan systems via sliding mode control**," *International Journal of Information Technology, Control and Automation*, Vol. 2, No. 2, pp 15- 25.
- [27] Chen, S.L., Chang, S.M., Lin, W.W. & Hwang, T. (2008) "**Digital secure communication using robust hyperchaotic systems**," *International Journal of Bifurcation and Chaos*, Vol. 18, No. 11, pp 3325-3339.
- [28] Xu, J., Cai, G. & Zheng, S. (2009) "**A novel hyperchaotic system and its control**", *J. Uncertain Systems*, Vol. 3, pp 137-144.
- [29] Chen, A., Lu, J., Lü, J. & Yu, S. (2006) "Generating hyperchaotic Lü attractor via state feedback control," *Physica A*, Vol. 364, pp 103-110.
- [30] Hahn, W. (1967) *The Stability of Motion*, Springer, New York.

Authors

Dr. V. Sundarapandian earned his Doctor of Science degree in Electrical and Systems Engineering from Washington University, Saint Louis, USA in 1996. He is a Professor at the Research and Development Centre, Vel Tech Dr. RR & Dr. SR Technical University, Chennai, Tamil Nadu, India. He has published over 260 refereed papers in international journals. He has published over 100 papers in National Conferences and over 60 papers in International Conferences. He is the Editor-in-Chief of the AIRCC Journals - International Journal of Instrumentation and Control Systems, International Journal of Control Systems and Computer Modelling, and International Journal of Information Technology, Control and Automation. His research interests are Linear and Nonlinear Control Systems, Chaos Theory and Control, Soft Computing, Optimal Control, Process Control, Operations Research, Mathematical Modelling, Scientific Computing using MATLAB and MATLAB.

A Survey on Data Mining in Steel Industries

S. Umeshini and C. P Sumathi,

SDNB Vaishnav College for Women, India

ABSTRACT

In Industrial environments, huge amount of data is being generated which in turn collected in database and data warehouses from all involved areas such as planning, process design, materials, assembly, production, quality, process control, scheduling, fault detection, shutdown, customer relation management, and so on. Data Mining has become a useful tool for knowledge acquisition for industrial process of Iron and steel making. Due to the rapid growth in Data Mining, various industries started using data mining technology to search the hidden patterns, which might further be used to the system with the new knowledge which might design new models to enhance the production quality, productivity optimum cost and maintenance etc. The continuous improvement of all steel production process regarding the avoidance of quality deficiencies and the related improvement of production yield is an essential task of steel producer. Therefore, zero defect strategy is popular today and to maintain it several quality assurance techniques are used. The present report explains the methods of data mining and describes its application in the industrial environment and especially, in the steel industry.

KEYWORDS

Repository, Explanatory variables, Clusters, Dependent variables, Ensemble methods, Decision making, patterns.

For More Details: <http://airconline.com/ijcses/V8N2/8217ijcses01.pdf>

Volume Link: <http://aircse.org/journal/ijcses/current2017.html>

REFERENCES

- [1] A.K. Choudhury, M.K. Tiwari and J.A Harding, (2009), '**Data Mining in Manufacturing: A review based on the kind of knowledge**'. Wolfson school mechanical and manufacturing engineering, Loughborough university, Loughborough, Leicestershire, UK, Journal of Intelligent manufacturing, 20(5), pp. 501-521.
- [2] Rosiane Mary Rezende Faleiro, Claudio Musso Velloso, Luiz Fernando Andrade De Castro, Ronaldo Santos Sampaio, (2013), '**Statistical modeling of charcoal consumption of blast furnace based on historical data**: Journal of Materials research and technology',2(4), 303– 307
- [3] Jiawei Han, Micheline Kamber, Jian Pei, (2012), **Data Mining: Concepts and Techniques**, Third Edition, USA, Morgan Kaufmann Publishers.
- [4] Nine law of Data Mining by Tom Khabaza (<http://www.kdnuggets.com/2015/16/nine-datamining-part-1.html>).
- [5] Hand D. J, Manila H, & Smyth, (2001): Principles of Data mining, MIT press, Cambridge, Massachusetts. ISN-262-08290-X
- [6] Aastha Joshi and Rajneet kaur, (2013), **A review: 'Comparative study of various clustering techniques in data mining'**, International Journal of Advanced Research in Computer Science and Software Engineering, Vol 3,2277 128x.
- [7] Manisha Verma, Mauly Srivastava, Neha Chack, Abul Kumar Diswar, Nidhi Gupta, (2012), 'Comparative study of various clustering algorithms in data mining'. International journal for engineering research and applications, Vol 2, Issue 3, pp. 1379-1384.
- [8] G.J Zheng, W. Zhang, P. Hu & D.Y SHI, (2015), Optimization of hot forming process using DMT and Finite element method, International Journal of Automotive Technology, Vol 16, no.2, pp: 329-337.
- [9] Stephen Dapiap, Gregory Wajiga, Michael Egwurube, Musa Kadzai, Nathaniel Oye &ThankGodAnazodo, (June2015), **Corrosion Control Approach using Data Mining**, International Journal of Computer Science & Information Technology(IJCSIT), vol 7, No 3.
- [10] Mahamad sarabee school of computing, science and Eng., university of Salford, greater Manchester, UK, Mehdi Moghimi, Dept. of Elec. & computer Eng., Islamic Azad university, Najafabad branch, Isfahan, Iran, Ayoub bagheri, Dept. of Elec and computer Eng, Isfahan university of technology, Isfahan Iran, (2011), Modeling Batch Annealing Process using Data Mining Techniques. ACM journal.
- [11] Sayed Mehran Sharafi, Hamid Reza Esamaely, (2005-2010), **Applying data mining methods to predict defects of steel surface**, Journal of theoretical and applied information technology, [www.jatit.org].
- [12] Michael Kommenda, Gabriel Kronberger Christoph Feilmayr and Michael Affenzeller, (23 Sep 2013), Data mining using unguided symbolic regression on a blast furnace dataset, arXiv;1309.5931v1 [cs.NE].
- [13] Michael Kommenda, Gabriel Kronberger, Christoph Feilmayr, Leonhard Schickmair, Michael Affenzeller, Stephan Winkler and Stefan Wagner, **Application of symbolic regression on blast furnace and temper mill datasets**, [n.d].
- [14] John R. Koza, Consulting Associate Professor in computer science department Stanford university, **Genetic programming: On the programming of computers by means of natural selection**, the MIT press [1992].
- [15] Jong-Hag Jeon, POSCO, Pohang South Korea, Data mining application of six-sigma project, SUGI 29 solutions, paper 186-29.

- [16] Ankit Agarwal, Parjit D Deshpande, Ahmet Cecen, Gautham P Basavarsu, Alok N Choudary and Surya R Kalidindi, (2014), Exploration of data science techniques to predict fatigue strength of steel from composition and processing parameters, Integrating materials and manufacturing innovation, 3:8, A springer open journal.
- [17] Fuxing Yu, Yina Suo, Xin Zang, Aidind Yan, Fulong Liu, (2013), Data mining in blast furnace smelting parameter, Applied mechanics and materials, vol. 303-306, pp 1093-1096.
- [18] Bjork, Holopainen, Wikstron, Saxen, Carelsson and Sihdonen, technical report number 1094, (Nov 2013), Analysis of blast furnace time series data with ANFIS: Turku center for computer science [TUCS].
- [19] Zheldak T.A, Slesarev V.V, Volovenko D.O, (2013), **Knowledge-based intellectual DSS of steel deoxidation in BOF production process**, American Journal of Mining and Metallurgy, Vol. 1, no.1, 7-10.
- [20] Veena Jokhakar, S.V Patel Ph.D., (March 2015), **A Review of Business Intelligence Techniques for Mild Steel Defect diagnosis**, International Journal of Computer applications (0975 – 8887), volume 113 – No 10.
- [21] Sanz-Garcia, F. Antonanzas-Torres, J. Fernandez-Ceniceros & F.J. Martinez-De-Pison (2014), Overall models based on ensemble methods for predicting continuous annealing furnace temperature settings, Iron and Steel Making, vol. 41, issue no 1.
- [22] Radu Platon & Mouloud Amazouz, From Report CETC – Varennes September 2007 -141 (TR), **Application of data mining techniques in Industrial Process Optimization**, Prepared by CANMET energy Technology Centre, <http://www.nrcan.gc.ca/2007-141e>.

A Kalman Filtering Tutorial for Undergraduate Students

Matthew B. Rhudy¹, Roger A. Salguero¹ and Keaton Holappa²,

¹Pennsylvania State University, USA and ²Bosch Rexroth Corporation, USA

ABSTRACT

This paper presents a tutorial on Kalman filtering that is designed for instruction to undergraduate students. The idea behind this work is that undergraduate students do not have much of the statistical and theoretical background necessary to fully understand the existing research papers and textbooks on this topic. Instead, this work offers an introductory experience for students which takes a more practical usage perspective on the topic, rather than the statistical derivation. Students reading this paper should be able to understand how to apply Kalman filtering tools to mathematical problems without requiring a deep theoretical understanding of statistical theory.

KEYWORDS

Data Processing, Kalman Filtering, Tutorial

For More Details: <http://airconline.com/ijcses/V8N1/8117ijcses01.pdf>

Volume Link: <http://airccse.org/journal/ijcses/current2017.html>

REFERENCES

- [1] Simon, D., Optimal State Estimation, Wiley, New York, 2006.
- [2] Anderson, B. D. O., and Moore, J. B., **Optimal Filtering**, Prentice-Hall, NJ, 1979.
- [3] Welch, G., and Bishop, G., “**An introduction to the Kalman filter**,” Technical Report TR 95-041, University of North Carolina, Department of Computer Science, 1995.
- [4] Kalman, R. E., “**A New Approach to Linear Filtering and Prediction Problems**,” Trans. of the ASME – Journal of Basic Engineering, March 1960, pp. 35-45.
- [5] Kreyszig, E., Advanced Engineering Mathematics, 9th Ed., Wiley, NY, 2006.
- [6] Reif, K., Günther, S., Yaz, E., and Unbehauen, R., “**Stochastic Stability of the Discrete-Time Extended Kalman Filter**,” IEEE Trans. on Automatic Control, Vol. 44, No. 4, April, 1999.
- [7] Jazwinski, A. H., Stochastic Processes and Filtering Theory, Academic, New York, 1970.
- [8] Hargrave, P., “A tutorial introduction to Kalman filtering,” IEEE Colloquium on Kalman Filters: Introduction, Applications and Future Developments, Feb. 1989.
- [9] Julier, S. and Uhlmann, J., “**A New Extension of the Kalman Filter to Nonlinear Systems**,” SPIE Proceedings Series, 1997, Vol. 3068, pp. 182-193.
- [10] Rhudy, M., and Gu, Y., “Understanding Nonlinear Kalman Filters, Part I: Selection between EKF and UKF,” Interactive Robotics Letters, West Virginia University, June 2013. Link: <http://www2.statler.wvu.edu/~irl/page13.html>.
- [11] Rhudy, M., Gu, Y., Gross, J., Gururajan, S., and Napolitano, M., “**Sensitivity Analysis of Extended and Unscented Kalman Filters for Attitude Estimation**,” AIAA Journal of Aerospace Information Systems, Vol. 10, No. 3, March 2013, pp. 131-143. doi: 10.2514/1.54899.
- [12] Gross, J., Gu, Y., Rhudy, M., Gururajan, S., and Napolitano, M., “**Flight Test Evaluation of GPS/INS Sensor Fusion Algorithms for Attitude Estimation**,” IEEE Transactions on Aerospace Electronic Systems, Vol. 48, No. 3, July 2012, pp. 2128-2139.
- [13] Rhudy, M., and Gu, Y., “Understanding Nonlinear Kalman Filters, Part II: An Implementation Guide,” Interactive Robotics Letters, West Virginia University, June 2013. Link: <http://www2.statler.wvu.edu/~irl/page13.html>.
- [14] Wan, E., and van der Merwe, R., “**The Unscented Kalman Filter**,” Chap. 7 in Kalman Filtering and Neural Networks, Wiley, New York, March 2002, pp. 221–282.

AUTHORS

Matthew Rhudy is currently an Assistant Professor in the Division of Engineering at the Pennsylvania State University, Berks Campus. Previously he was a Visiting Assistant Professor at Lafayette College in Easton, PA for 2 years. He received a Ph.D. in Aerospace Engineering from West Virginia University in 2013, a M.S. in Mechanical Engineering from the University of Pittsburgh in 2009, and a B.S. in Mechanical Engineering from the Pennsylvania State University in 2008.

Roger Salguero is an undergraduate mechanical engineering student at the Pennsylvania State University, Berks Campus. He is working on unmanned aircraft research through the Erickson Discovery Grant as well as the Frank Franco Undergraduate Research Award.

Keaton Holappa received a B.S. in Mechanical Engineering and a B.A. in Art from Lafayette College in 2016. He specializes in control theory, and is working on research related to the stability of micro-quadcopter swarms responding to musical inputs.

